

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERIO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETEN- SCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

The Polifonia Web portal is an aggregator of data belonging to digital musical heritage collections. The tasks relevant to the development of the Polifonia Web portal include the following:

- **Cataloguing.** A reference registry of Music Heritage resources, including but not limited to all collections used and produced in the project. By extending musoW¹ [1], a catalogue of Musical Data on the Web, this task provides a new online catalogue of digital projects, data sources, archives relevant to several music-related tasks (e.g. musicology, education, journalism)².
- **Crowdsourcing.** Methods for automatic and semiautomatic generation of metadata according to the Polifonia ontologies. The task produced CLEF³, a platform for Linked Open Data creation and curation, and synchronised with GitHub and Zenodo for long-term preservation (the software is used to publish musoW);
- **Discovery.** Methods for continuous indexing of Music Heritage resources. The task has produced a pipeline⁴ for the discovery of music archives on the web that is to be included into musoW.
- **Design and exploration** Methods for searching, querying, and browsing Music Heritage resources. The task developed (1) a graphic prototype of a Web portal⁵ to disseminate research results to a broad audience, and (2) a tool for creating data stories and dashboards⁶, for a more data-driven exploration of research results of Polifonia pilots.

Both the activities and the document here presented received methodological inputs from partners of WP1 (described in *D1.2 Roadmap and pilot requirements*), WP5 (described in *D5.2 Interactive Tools for searching, browsing and exploration*), and the Data Management Plan (*D7.2 Updated Data Management Plan*). This task also provided input to WP6 *D6.2 Plan for Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results* on recommendations for the sustainability of Polifonia outcomes beyond the lifespan of the project.

Results described in this deliverable are summarised in table 0.1.

¹<http://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/>

²<http://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/>

³https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app

⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/musow-pipeline>

⁵https://github.com/polifonia-project/web_portal

⁶<https://github.com/polifonia-project/dashboard>

ID	DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5603223
Type	Dataset
Name	musoW
Credits	M. Daquino (UNIBO), E. Daga (OU), A. Meronyo Penuela (KCL), M. d'Aquin (NUIG), et al.
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app
Release	v0.1.4
License	CC0
ID	DOI:10.5281/zenodo.6423933
Type	Software
Name	CLEF, Crowdsourcing Linked Entities via web Form
Credits	Marilena Daquino (UNIBO), Enrico Daga (UNIBO), Mari Wigham (NISV)
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/clef
Release	v1.0.0
License	ISC
ID	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6501307
Type	Software
Name	musoW discovery pipeline
Credits	Laurent Fintoni (UNIBO), Marilena Daquino (UNIBO), Jacopo de Berardinis (KCL)
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/musow-pipeline
Release	v0.1
License	ISC
ID	https://zenodo.org/badge/latest/doi/431529042
Type	Software
Name	MELODY, Make mE a Linked Open DatastorY
Credits	Giulia Renda (UNIBO), Marilena Daquino (UNIBO), et al.
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/dashboard
Release	v0.1
License	ISC
ID	-
Type	Prototype
Name	Web portal mockup
Credits	Marco Grasso (UNIBO), Marilena Daquino (UNIBO), et al.
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/web_portal/tree/main/prototypes
Release	-
License	CC-BY
ID	-
Type	Prototype
Name	Dashboard templates for data stories
Credits	Giulia Manganelli (UNIBO), Marilena Daquino (UNIBO), et al.
Source code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/web_portal/tree/main/prototypes
Release	-
License	CC-BY

Table 0.1: Software and prototypes described in this deliverable

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
V0.1	10/05/2022	First draft released	UNIBO
V0.2	20/6/2022	Draft revised by internal reviewers	UNIBO, NISV, NUIG
V1.0	30/6/2022	Final version submitted	UNIBO

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1 Introduction

To date, several aggregators of cultural heritage data exist, such as [Europeana](#), [PHAROS](#), that collect data from institutions, scholars, and experts, and serve high-quality information to stakeholders. In the last decade, many infrastructures embraced the usage of Semantic Web technologies to comply with a number of requirements, such as the production of findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data that can be easily leveraged by external applications or projects, and the creation of powerful services and web applications to engage with patrons. Similarly, the objective of the Polifonia Web portal is to collect and disseminate data relevant to music heritage on the web, including results produced by the project, such as data and metadata created by pilots, and assets produced beyond Polifonia. Linked Open Data and RDF [2] model have been chosen as the *lingua franca* to be used to share data and to build the Knowledge Graph of Musical Heritage.

However, several problems affect the design and development of a comprehensive platform for engaging with users and experts passionate about music. In Polifonia we have identified four main issues and sub-tasks. Three sub-tasks are relevant to the creation and maintenance of a registry of music resources (namely: cataloguing, crowdsourcing, and discovery), and one task relevant to the dissemination of music data to a broad audience (design and exploration). Issues, tasks, and our goals can be summarised as follows:

- **Cataloguing** The scope of Digital Music Heritage is broad and diverse, and mapping the landscape of music data on the web is challenging. No comprehensive catalogue of music digital collections is available, and it is not easy to estimate the scale of the problem. When data is available, it is not always possible to programmatically access it and reuse it in third-party applications. musoW [1] is a one-off attempt to survey music data on the web, and it is not meant to systematically catalogue European Music Heritage. In Polifonia we rely on this prior work to create a comprehensive, ongoing, online registry of music data and release results as a Linked Open Dataset.
- **Crowdsourcing** Producing high-quality, crowdsourced (linked open) data is challenging. It requires time-consuming data production activities, such as data curation, data management workflow, and planning data sustainability. Unfortunately, state-of-the-art software solutions for Linked Data production are not suitable for this task (see sec. 2). In Polifonia we develop a web application for crowdsourcing LOD according to Polifonia ontologies, and guaranteeing data preservation.
- **Discovery** Manual cataloguing and data curation to keep the registry updated is an expensive task and may not be sustainable in the long run. In Polifonia we develop a pipeline for music data discovery, automatically producing recommendations of web resources to be included in the registry.
- **Design and exploration** Catalogues are specialised services that can serve a rather small target audience (e.g. music journalists, librarians). Instead, the Polifonia web portal aims at developing web solutions to (1) reach lay people genuinely interested in serendipitous discovery in music heritage, and (2) drive scholars into a more data-driven exploratory approach to answer research questions. We design a web portal that targets non-specialist users, curious and passionate users, and domain experts. The portal, designed in a magazine-style fashion, is supported by data-driven insights and dashboards for storytelling.

The motivation of our work relies on the general need for reusable solutions to manage domain-(in)dependent knowledge life cycle, spanning from data creation and curation, to discovery, enrichment, dissemination, and preservation.

The remainder of the report is the following. In section 2 we review relevant works for each of the four outlined tasks, and we highlight which gaps we aim to fill in. In section 3 we outline objectives, results, and their status at the due date of this deliverable (see Table 3.1). For each task we present our methodology and approach. In section 4 we present results, including references to online materials and applications and their evaluation. In section 5 we discuss results, their exploitability and limitations, and we present the plan for future works.

2 State of the art

2.1 Cataloguing: Music Heritage on the Web

The landscape of collaborative projects in the Cultural Heritage domain is broad. Several participation models are in place, such as crowdsourcing campaigns, and scholarly collaborative projects [3]. In recent years, a few initiatives to collaboratively create registries or catalogues relevant to music scholarship have been proposed. Most initiatives have produced lists of useful resources, such as MusoRepo¹ to share digital resources for musicology, Awesome MIDI to collaboratively aggregate MIDI collections on the Web², ISMIR datasets³ to collect data for Music Information Retrieval, DH ontologies⁴ including a section devoted to musicology data models, or Music Journalism Insider⁵, a newsletter for music journalism. More systematic data collection projects include the following resources.

MuSO⁶ is a collaborative project that currently aggregates digital libraries, Europeana Music Collection, and literary and historical content from the Advanced Research Consortium (ARC) database. Data are described according to a customised version of the ARC/RDF schema⁷, with a focus on notated music. However, data access is not granted, or it is not immediately obvious how to retrieve collected data for reuse. The online catalogue allows to search for born-digital resources via text search. However the search seems to be limited to collections of the 18th century, and the query service is hosted in an external source whose scope includes also non music-related artefacts. It is not immediately apparent what can be found, and what is the extent of the collection that can be searched. The project is not maintained since 2018, and it is unclear whether any form of contribution is still possible.

musoW 1.0[1] is a survey of digital music collections, such as digital libraries, archives, datasets, but also software, vocabularies, and scholarly projects. The dataset includes around 350 resources, described according to a custom vocabulary that partially reuses existing ontologies (such as DC, VoiD, Schema.org, DCAT). Differently from MuSO, in musoW mainly cataloguing information are provided, while very few insights on the scope and contents are provided. The online catalogue provides both an overview of contents⁸ and several access points to the data, such as browsing interfaces, a full-text search, and a GUI to the SPARQL endpoint. The project has not been maintained since 2017 but anonymous contributions are possible via a google form.

Music DH 2021⁹ is a recent attempt to collect information on Digital Humanities projects relevant to music scholarship. The collection includes 186 resources, significantly overlapping resources described in musoW, described with a small set of fields useful to identify resources and provide references for their access. The list is available for reuse as a downloadable csv file¹⁰, and can be searched by keyword.

In summary, scattered attempts to create a curated registry of online music resources exist. However, these generally fail in providing (1) a comprehensive catalogue, (2) detailed information on contents of surveyed resources, (3) 5-stars data that rely on standard or popular vocabularies, and (4) user-friendly strategies to explore data or means to programmatically access data. Among the surveyed resources *musow 1.0* is the most comprehensive and reusable catalogue, and it is therefore our starting point to create a new catalogue.

¹<https://fourscoreandmore.org/musoRepo/>

²<https://github.com/albertmeronyo/awesome-midi-sources/>

³<https://www.ismir.net/resources/datasets/>

⁴<https://github.com/CLARIAH/awesome-humanities-ontologies>

⁵<https://docs.google.com/document/d/ln6YzY38xxPs8Uz2dNxPQgSPQTWODBfxckLueVgcb-ds/edit?usp=sharing>

⁶<https://muso.arts.gla.ac.uk/index.html>

⁷http://wiki.collex.org/index.php/Submitting_RDF

⁸<https://musow.kmi.open.ac.uk/browse>

⁹<https://rutgersdh.github.io/musicdh/>

¹⁰<https://rutgersdh.github.io/musicdh/reuse/>

2.2 Crowdsourcing: curating Linked Open Data

Collaborative projects and crowdsourcing campaigns may require limited contributions from users, like *social tagging*, record linkage, data curation. In such scenarios, adequate tools for data collection and strategies for data curation, publication, and preservation must be found at the beginning of the project.

Omeka S¹¹ is a platform for data collection and creation of virtual exhibitions. While user groups can be defined, editors do not have the means to supervise the peer-review process, and changes made by contributors as well as records under review must be managed separately. Records (*items*) are served as JSON-LD documents via API, but cannot be accessed in any other RDF serialisation, nor queried via a SPARQL endpoint, which may be cumbersome in data analysis tasks. Exports can be requested on demand, but no mechanism for versioning is active. Moreover, the visibility of records can be constantly modified, thereby hindering the continuity of services relying on data served by the application. The software is open source, actively developed and maintained by a broad community and serves several projects in the Cultural Heritage domain.

Semantic MediaWiki¹² is a popular tool used by Wikipedia, which allows data to be displayed in a catalogue fashion. New records can be created via web forms and external sources can be used to populate fields when dedicated plugins are installed. The system enables fine-grained editorial control and serves data as LOD, which are stored in a triplestore. Semantic MediaWiki is open source, actively maintained, and supported by a broad community.

Sinopia¹³ is a web-based environment developed by the LD4P (Linked Data for Production) initiative, based on Library of Congress's BIBFRAME Editor and Profile Editor¹⁴. Sinopia potentially supports other ontologies than BIBFRAME, and users can customize templates for the creation of RDF triples via web forms. Unfortunately, Sinopia does not provide a fully-fledged editorial workflow. In fact, provenance information must be recorded manually by cataloguers, and is otherwise not stored along with data. Like in OmekaS, data are stored in a relational database and are shared via APIs that serve JSON-LD documents. The software is currently under development.

ResearchSpace¹⁵ is a web platform for creating collections as LOD. The platform is optimised to build exhibitions and sophisticated user templates. While providing flexibility to customise templates according to Linked Data patterns, unfortunately, an expert user is needed to encode such preferences using a custom templating language. Likewise, the entire setup of the back-end functionalities requires the templating system to be manually setup. Notably, when creating new records, provenance information is stored. Linked Data are stored in a triplestore and a SPARQL endpoint is provided. Assets like ontologies and vocabularies can be versioned by configuring a Git repository. Data can be uploaded to the triplestore via the back-end, and can be manipulated with visual authoring tools (e.g. image annotators, PDF annotators, graphical network editor). The software is based on Metaphactory [4], a commercial enterprise product, customised to comply with the requirements of supporters.

In summary, existing solutions fail in coping with some of the following aspects: (1) user-friendly ways to build interfaces, (2) provenance management, (3) integration with existing data management workflow (e.g. versioning, backup, long-term preservation), and (4) reusability and sustainability of produced assets and software. However, these aspects are deemed fundamental to ensure the registry produces high quality data in a sustainable manner.

2.3 Discovery: sustainable methods for collecting new web resources

The ability to continuously discover new domain-specific content from the Web is critical for many applications. Existing solutions include the development of focused crawlers, which can be time-consuming and expensive to maintain. Domain experts usually provide a list of relevant websites to be used as training examples for creating a classifier that recognizes relevant pages, as well as a set of pages to seed the crawl.

¹¹<https://omeka.org/s/>.

¹²https://www.semantic-mediawiki.org/wiki/Semantic_MediaWiki.

¹³<https://sinopia.io>

¹⁴<https://bibframe.org>

¹⁵<https://https://researchspace.org/>

Keyword-based search operators submit keyword search queries to search engines (e.g. Bing, Google), extract keywords from the result pages classified as relevant for the domain, and use these keywords to construct new search queries. Results of prior works [5] show that multiple small queries obtain better results than submitting long queries. However, the classifier needs a large curated training set to prevent the search results quickly diverging from the domain at hand. Moreover, usually such approaches do not combine results with other discovery methods, such as crawling-based operators.

Crawling-based operators adopt methods like forward-crawling, where links are extracted from the seed web pages to detect new relevant sources. Crawlers usually use two classifiers: a *critic* classifier that categorizes web pages as relevant, and an *apprentice* classifier that learns to identify the most promising links in a page. Compared to search-based techniques, forward crawling is more scalable, however, it works better for domains where relevant content is well-connected [6]. Moreover, the critic classifier given as input to the system requires a substantial number of positive and negative examples to be trained on.

Approaches to real-time discovery [7, 8] make use of social media platforms (e.g., Twitter) to monitor and track domain-specific content, trends and topic evolution. Most crawling solutions do not use social-media feeds to discover web pages. Nonetheless, social media feeds could be used to extract links and therefore provide seeds to a crawler and classifier.

Text classification is a well-known task, and several strategies exist to categorise discovered resources. Among those, Logistic Regression and TF-IDF are considered *traditional* word-based approaches, which lately have been replaced by more sophisticated approaches. Nonetheless, these methods have demonstrated being a successful solution to solve binary classification problems - with both long and short texts [9] - and are currently considered to perform as well as (or even outperforming) modern embedding-based approaches, such as language models [10].

In summary, existing discovery methods (1) require an extensive training set to produce a reliable classifier, (2) do not combine keyword-based searches with forward-crawlers, and (3) do not make use of social media to collect seeds. Instead, in Polifonia we aim at maintaining the registry of music resources in real-time, hence requiring new discoveries to be found and included in a timely manner. Secondly, consolidated methods for text classification are an excellent starting point for music resource classification, in order to produce a sustainable and easy to deploy solution to be integrated in the online catalogue. To the best of our knowledge, bespoke solutions for music data discovery based on social media feeds are not available.

2.4 Design and exploration: music heritage interfaces and Linked Data storytelling

Generous interfaces have been increasingly discussed in the Digital Humanities debate as a way to support casual users browsing a collection and reveal its structure and complexity [11]. Casual users that stumble into digital collections usually do not have enough expertise to grasp scope, content, and how to search the collection [12]. Research on casual users' information needs when browsing digital cultural heritage collections suggests that many visitors approach digital artefacts without a clear goal in mind. Rather, they are driven by a desire for something interesting or challenging, as confirmed by several studies [13, 14] and user surveys¹⁶. Generally, such users adopt an exploratory approach and seem to enjoy the research process itself [14] rather than the achievement and the result. Likewise, when observing information visualizations, non-experts look for basic patterns, to gain a feeling for the data, and to reflect on its social and personal relevance [15].

In contrast, experts are moved by hypotheses, and seek for specific answers. Therefore, task-driven interfaces seem to be optimal solutions for them [16]. **Exploratory interfaces for Linked Open Data** are increasingly produced in the Cultural Heritage domain to comply with expert users' analytical needs. These include solutions for browsing dataset content, showing interconnections, and full-stack solutions for data visualizations [17]. In recent works [18] 77 Linked Data visualization tools have been surveyed and evaluated. Results show that such tools are not sufficiently equipped for providing full support to users who want to explore and gain knowledge from Linked Data. Some issues regard scalability, the provision of dataset statistics beyond generic counters, and the possibility to combine different visualizations into a user-defined narrative.

¹⁶Europeana User survey 2014, <https://www.slideshare.net/Europeana/europeana-user-survey-2014-report>

In summary, current research in digital heritage interfaces tends to focus on (1) exploratory interfaces for enjoyment, serendipity, and entertainment of lay people, and (2) hypotheses-driven Linked Open Data analytical tools for experts. In Polifonia we would like to address these two main challenges related to music information visualization, namely: (1) how music heritage collections can be visualized for public use, and (2) how experts can interact with hypotheses-driven data stories. While principles of generous interfaces come in handy in designing interfaces for lay people, effective tools for Linked Data exploration and storytelling are missing.

3 Research problems, objectives, and approach

3.1 Research problems and objectives

From the state of the art emerged a few challenges relevant to our four research areas, namely:

- **Cataloguing** A comprehensive online catalogue of music scholarship is missing. Likewise, tools to explore the landscape of music data on the web are scattered and data are not always easy to access.
- **Crowdsourcing** Methods to produce 5-star data¹ require time-consuming and expensive activities to set up an environment for crowdsourcing and data enrichment, and lack sustainable strategies for data management.
- **Discovery** While automated solutions are not yet adequate, manual collection of domain-specific resources to populate a dataset is an expensive and not sustainable task for mid-long term projects.
- **Design and exploration** On the one hand, digital cultural heritage collections are often dedicated to specialists, and fail in engaging with lay people. On the other hand, solutions to enable experts to analyse Linked Data and share data stories are missing.

In table 3.1 we present long-term objectives (to be achieved by the end of the project); intermediate objectives, to be achieved by M18; and a reference to results described in section 4. Intermediate objectives and results are the target of this deliverable.

Problem	Long-term objectives	M18 objectives	M18 results
Cataloguing	Registry on music data: >1k	Manually-curated registry: <1k	musoW 2.0 (sec. 4.1)
Crowdsourcing	Platform for LOD publication	Platform for LOD publication	CLEF (sec. 4.2)
Discovery	Pipeline for data discovery	Pipeline v1	Pipeline (sec. 4.3)
Design and e.	Web portal of Polifonia	UI/UX prototype	Prototype (sec. 4.4.1)
Design and e.	Dashboard for data storytelling	Software for LOD storytelling	MELODY (sec. 4.4.2)
Design and e.	Templates for data stories	UI/UX prototype	Prototypes (sec. 4.4.2)

Table 3.1: Long-term goals, intermediate goals and results

3.2 Approach and work plan

3.2.1 Cataloguing

To design and populate the registry of music data sources, we undertook the following actions.

- **Requirements collection.** We discussed with internal members of Polifonia and we interviewed external stakeholders, such as music journalists, librarians, and scholars involved in similar projects. We collected insights on the music sources and collections that they use on a daily basis, and what requirements a registry should comply with.
- **Data modelling.** We reviewed the ontology used in musoW and defined a new specification, mainly based on schema.org. We defined provenance and knowledge representation requirements, and we identified the [PROV](#) ontology and named graphs as best candidates to represent crowdsourced descriptions of resources.

¹<https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

- **Data survey.** We collected resources made available by people we interviewed, and resources already available in musoW and music DH. We gathered around 200 sources from a music journalist, which were manually checked. musoW and Music DH significantly overlap in their scope, although musoW was revealed being broader and richer in terms of descriptions. We gathered around 350 resources, which were automatically extracted from the SPARQL endpoint.
- **Data ingestion and publication.** We collected descriptions and metadata about resources in a table, and we transformed the data into Linked Open Data according to the application profile of schema.org that we designed. We published an initial dataset online using CLEF, the tool we developed to facilitate data entry, publication and long-term preservation (see below).
- **Boost data entry.** We organised a mini-workshop with Polifonia members to boost data entry and get feedback on the online catalogue.

Requirements collection. To systematically collect requirements for musoW, we adopted **eXtreme Design** [19] (see also D1.2, D2.1, and D5.2), the ontology design methodology used by all partners of the project. eXtreme Design (XD) has been selected as an ontology engineering methodology since it provides methodological support for incrementally addressing small sets of requirements and for minimizing the impact of changes in incremental releases, hence it's specifically useful for a project, as Polifonia, which aims at addressing a huge and diverse domain. The methodology requires to have interviews with stakeholders so as to define goals, research questions, and data requirements. The result is usually the creation of one or more *personas*, described via one or more stories, and a number of competency questions (CQs) that the ontology, the data, and the application serving the data, should provide an answer to.

To define the **objectives of the registry**, we interviewed a music journalist, who produces a weekly newsletter² on archives and research resources that deal with music in some way, and a Digital Humanities Librarian involved in music scholarship projects like muSO and music DH 2021 (see section 2), so as to collect initial requirements relevant to our target users. From their feedback we created a new persona, called Laurent³. The competency questions can be summarised as follows:

- CQ1: Can I search for a musical content by applying filters (genre, historical period ...)?
- CQ2: What types of resources can I find?
- CQ3: Is the description of the music resource X complete or incomplete?
- CQ4: Is a dataset attached to resource X?
- CQ5: Can I add resources as a user?
- CQ6: How can I share what I find on the website?

Data modelling. The competency questions are first used to develop an ontology in a bottom-up approach, together with content requirements collected from existing similar solutions (top-down approach). To define the **type of resources** to be described in the registry, we surveyed existing competitors, namely, musoW, MuSO, and Music DH 2021, as described in section 2. We included in the scope of the registry scholarly projects, collections of music contents (like datasets, digital libraries, repositories of scores, digital editions) and software solutions useful to manipulate music data (i.e., symbolic music, audio, and bibliographic or historical metadata). We excluded resources that do not serve any form of music data, such as informative websites, online radios, and so on.

To define the **scope of metadata** to be addressed for catalogued resources, we estimated a reasonable level of detail including (1) fields that are addressed by more than one similar project, (2) fields that we need in order to access the described resources (e.g. links to APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and data dumps), and (3) provenance information on the information provider (creators and modifiers of the record). A working group iteratively discussed the metadata schema, and selected terms from [Schema.org](https://schema.org/) to be associated with descriptive fields, and from the PROV Ontology [20] to describe provenance information. Schema.org and PROV were selected because of their broad scope, that nicely overlapped with metadata requirements of the registry, for their popularity and for being a W3-endorsed standard respectively. Fields, descriptions, and mapped ontology terms are collected in a [table](#). These

²Music Journalism Insider newsletter, <https://www.musicjournalisminsider.com/>

³Laurent's story, <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories/tree/main/Laurent:%20Music%20Journalist>

include, among others, fields like *name*, *URL*, *description*, *creator*, *resource type*, *resource example (if collection)*, *purpose*, *audience*, *spatial/temporal/artist/genre scope*, *access*, *license*, *formats*, *music features described*, *services* - such as APIs, SPARQL endpoints, data dumps. Provenance-related fields include *record publisher*, *contributor*, *date of publication and modification*.

Data survey. Once the schema had been defined, we collected a **first dataset** including around 350 resource descriptions, that we gathered in a [table](#) and collaboratively reviewed. Collected data include resources from musoW and, partially, Music DH 2021, which both release data under a CC0 waiver.

Data ingestion and publication. We performed a one-off transformation of data into RDF according to Schema.org and PROV using a [Python Jupyter notebook](#) and we uploaded the final dataset to the [online SPARQL endpoint](#) of the registry, which serves data to the website for exploring and populating the registry. The dataset thereby created is published online via CLEF, the Linked Open Data native cataloguing system developed by Polifonia to crowdsource music resources descriptions and publish an interactive registry (see section 4.2 for details on the application functionalities).

3.2.2 Crowdsourcing

To facilitate the continuous ingestion of data, their management, and their publication, we developed a dedicated software solution, called CLEF. We proceeded as follows:

- **Requirements collection** We collected requirements that emerged during dedicated meetings with music experts and developers. We analysed another project with similar requirements, ARTchives, to ensure completeness and soundness of requirements. We compared existing solutions for data collection, publication, and preservation on the basis of our requirements (results shown in sec. 4).
- **Development** We developed CLEF, a software solution that complies with our requirements.
- **Testing** We tested the software with developers who are part of the consortium. During the mini-workshop to boost data entry, we collected feedback from other members of the consortium on the usability of the interfaces for data collection and exploration.
- **Evaluation** We benchmarked existing solutions for Linked Data publication and we highlighted gaps in complying with our requirements.

Requirements collection CLEF has been designed with a bottom-up approach, taking into account user requirements collected from two case studies, namely: an external project called ARTchives [21] representative of crowdsourcing campaigns promoted by cultural institutions; and musoW, representative of collaborative data collections in scholarly projects. We selected this external case study because of the many similarities with musoW in terms of requirements, although having a completely different scope (art historians' archives), hence a good testbed for the software. Whenever applicable, such requirements have been translated into Linked Open Data requirements or functionalities. Requirements can be summarised as follows.

- **Findability.** Data are identified with persistent identifiers (URIs), described with rich metadata, and are findable in the Web.
 - *Discoverability.* Allow search engines to leverage structured data for indexing purposes. Every record is served as HTML5 documents including RDFa annotations.
 - *Exploration.* Automatically generate data views to facilitate retrieval. Operations for automatically generating views, such as filtering, grouping, and sorting, are available. These are ontology-driven, i.e. the result of SPARQL queries.
- **Accessibility.** Data are accessible via the HTTP protocol, and are available in the long term via a plethora of solutions for programmatic data access.
 - *Preservation (sources).* Request digital preservation of user-specified resources. Rely on established services like the WayBack machine⁴ for web archiving.

⁴<https://archive.org/web/>

Preservation (ontologies). Allow direct reuse of up-to-date schemas and data of existing projects. Retrieve information on the user-defined data model from the Linked Open Vocabularies initiative [22].

Preservation (data). Integrate the system with established data management workflows. Bind changes in Linked Data to commits in GitHub and release versions in Zenodo.

- *Persistence.* Ensure continuity of services built on top of generated data. Prevent deletion of published records identified with persistent URIs.
- **Interoperability.** Data are served in standard serialisations, include references to standard or popular ontologies, and links to external sources. While this was not an explicit requirement highlighted from use cases, it is a natural consequence of the usage of Linked Open Data, which makes it easier to work with data (e.g. in data integration over multiple sources).
- **Reusability.** Data are released as open data with non-restrictive licenses, are associated with detailed provenance information and follow well-known data sharing policies.
 - *Enhancement.* Generate structured data from natural language texts. Perform Named Entity Recognition over long texts on demand, extract structured data, and reconcile to Wikidata to avoid users to repeat information in different fields.
 - *Consistency.* Ensure interlinking of records and correct usage of terminology. Suggest terms from selected LOD sources and user-specified controlled vocabularies while creating new records. Allow contradictory information to be recorded as named graphs. Ensure peer-review mechanisms are enabled to supervise contributions from non-experts, and prevent inconsistencies in the final user application. Allow restriction of access, and give privileges to a group of users that share ownership of data on GitHub.
 - *Accuracy.* Allow fine-grained curatorial intervention on crowdsourced data. Represent records as named graphs and annotate graphs with provenance information according to the PROV ontology (including contributors, dates, and activities/stages in the peer-review process). Update annotations every time a change happens in the graphs. Track changes and responsibilities in GitHub commits.
 - *Validation.* Allow automatic validation of data. Along with manual curation, perform schema and instance level checks to ensure created data conform to user-generated (ontology-based) templates.

Moreover, while not in the scope of FAIR principles, the use cases highlighted that in order to prevent error-prone operations (e.g. data reconciliation), guarantee high-level data quality standards, and serve easy-to-find data, **user-friendly interfaces** are highly recommended. Therefore, the provision of easy-to-use interfaces becomes a fundamental user requirement of CLEF to ensure (1) reusability of data and easiness of exploration for the final user, and (2) simplicity and error avoidance for editors and administrators.

Development The software has been **developed in two phases**. An initial data management system was developed for ARTchives⁵. In a second phase, the code base has been extended and adapted to be customizable and reusable as-is in other crowdsourcing projects. CLEF is developed in Python, based on [Web.py](#), a simple and small-size framework for web applications. The source code of CLEF is available on GitHub⁶ and Zenodo [23].

Testing The initial version of the system was tested with around 15 cataloguers of the six institutions promoting the ARTchives project, namely: the Federico Zeri Foundation (Bologna), Bibliotheca Hertziana (Rome), Getty Research Institute (Los Angeles), Kunsthistorisches Institut in Florenz (Florence), Scuola Normale Superiore (Pisa), and Università Roma Tre (Rome). We performed new user tests on the revised version of the software (CLEF), with both developers and consumers that are partners of Polifonia. Now user tests are continuously performed by Polifonia project members, who provide new requirements to foster development and research, documented in the repository issue tracker⁷. User tests will soon be performed with users with different profiles and less technical experience.

Evaluation We surveyed existing open-source software solutions that are popular in the cultural heritage and Digital humanities domain (detailed in section 2) to understand whether our requirements could be satisfied by reusing out-of-the-box solutions. We therefore identified a gap in the state of the art that we aimed to fill in by developing CLEF.

⁵ARTchives source code is available at: <https://github.com/marilenadaquino/ARTchives>

⁶CLEF source code available at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/clef/releases/latest>, ISC license.

⁷Issue tracker https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app/issues

We evaluated our work by comparing features proposed by CLEF to prior works and we highlighted both benefits and limitations.

3.2.3 Discovery

To foster the semi-automatic population of musoW we realized a music data recommender, including a social-media scraper and a music resource classifier. We undertook the following actions.

- **Keyword extraction** In order to create a pool of search queries, we extracted recurring keywords (bi-grams) in music resource descriptions from musoW and Music Journalism Insider newsletter.
- **Training sets creation** We created two training sets, respectively for tweets including references to music resources and music resource descriptions.
- **Classifiers and models creation** We created two classifiers, to respectively (1) detect relevant tweets and (2) categorise resources referenced in tweets.
- **Recommendation pipeline** We created a pipeline that includes a Twitter search (based on keyword list) to retrieve tweets mentioning web resources, a classifier of tweets, a web scraper of links referenced in tweets, and a classifier of web pages. Results are stored in a spreadsheet for user selection.

Keyword extraction Currently, musoW includes around 500 positive examples of music resources (i.e. good examples of descriptions). Music Journalism Insider (MJI) newsletter includes several resources already described in musoW, and around 200 new descriptions. We performed a one-time query to both the datasets to retrieve titles, URLs, and descriptions and we extracted a list of most and least recurring bi-grams (see the [Jupyter notebook](#) and the [final keyword list](#)).

Training sets creation. We used most and least common bi-grams in musoW and MJI to query Twitter and collect a set of positive/negative tweets targeting music resources (i.e. targeting tweets including links to candidate resources to be included in musoW and not). In detail, the list of most recurring bi-grams is used to perform searches on Twitter archive, via the [Academic twitter API](#), and to retrieve candidate positive examples. We pruned tweets that did not include any link, hence not referencing any online music resource, and we included tweets content and referenced URLs in the training set of positive examples. To collect negative examples we looked for tweets that are similar to our positive target but pointing to resources that are out of scope (e.g. tweets targeting artists' playlists, fun pages, music companies), and tweets targeting similar but broader content, such as *Digital Humanities* projects, identified using the least common and more generic bi-grams (e.g. *manuscript database*, *university archive*). The result is a perfectly balanced training set of 8758 tweets, including 4379 positive and negative tweets respectively.

The training set for music resource classification includes text descriptions of web resources that we deem relevant to musoW, namely: music archives, data collections, and software. We collected resource descriptions from musoW and MJI newsletter to create a set of positive examples. To collect negative examples, we scraped webpages referenced in tweets that are part of the Twitter training set classified as negative. The result is a balanced dataset of 1070 descriptions, (544 positive/ 526 negative examples). All [training sets](#) are available online.

Classifiers and model creation We created two models to classify tweets and resource descriptions respectively. Both the models use Logistic Regression to classify relevant and non relevant examples, and use TF-IDF as feature. Considering our task, we need a good balance between precision and recall, so that manual selection of recommendations is faster and not demotivating for reviewers. We trained and ran the classifiers on the training sets and we created a model for predicting new relevant tweets/web resources. [Pickled models](#) are available online.

Recommendation pipeline We combined the aforementioned components into a pipeline that performs searches on Twitter, returns relevant posts and web contents and returns recommendations on music resources to be included in musoW. A full evaluation is postponed to later stages of the project. Currently, we evaluated the prediction model and a sample of recommendations to estimate precision and recall.

3.2.4 Design and exploration.

In order to design a web portal targeted to lay people and experts, we undertook the following activities:

- **Competency questions analysis** We performed a data layer analysis to frame scope and priorities of the web portal. Secondly we performed a user-oriented analysis of Competency Questions (CQs) to frame informative needs and expectations with respect to target groups (top-down approach).
- **Competitive analysis** We reviewed online competitors in terms of UI/UX design choices.
- **Focus groups** We collected expectations and frustration elements in competitors (bottom-up approach).
- **Web portal prototyping** Iterative sketching of architecture, services, content design, graphics. Mockups have been evaluated with scholars in Polifonia.

The connection between the ontology design methodology and the UI/UX design methodology is shared with WP5, and it is fully described in D5.2. To specifically target scholars, we refined strategies for a data-driven exploration of the Polifonia knowledge graph, consisting of a flexible dashboarding system and a number of templates for designing data stories.

- **Dashboard development** We developed a user-friendly interface to allow pilots to produce data stories targeted to experts.
- **Templates prototyping** We designed a systematic approach to address personas, and identify most common templates for data-driven stories.
- **Testing** We tested the software with developers and we evaluated the mockups (web portal and dashboard) with scholars in Polifonia.

Competency questions analysis The requirements analysis is an iterative process, moving from an overview of pilots' scope and commonalities to a detailed representation of each pilot's scope, targets, and informative needs. By performing content analysis over competency questions and stories collected in the project, we extracted structured information on entities, relations and we produced data visualizations of shared information patterns (i.e. entities addressed in similar questions regardless of the pilot they belong to), interaction patterns (i.e. tasks and browsing habits).

Pilots overview. We asked representatives in Polifonia to provide an estimate of subjects of interest and related information characterising their pilot project ([benchmark table](#)) and we extracted a view of overlapping concepts.

Scope and information patterns We collected all CQs described in [stories](#) and we annotated them with (1) a classification of the data required to answer the CQ (i.e. bibliographic and historical data, linguistic data, music structured data), (2) main entities involved (i.e. ontology classes) and simplified trajectories (i.e. ontology predicate paths) between them ([annotated table](#)) that emerged from the benchmark (see an example in Fig. 3.1). We performed a preliminary analysis to frame the scope of the web portal in terms of most represented personas and priorities for the development ([Jupyter notebook](#)). In summary:

- **Bibliographic and historical data** are fundamental to answer 70% of CQs.
- **Music data** cover 36% of CQs. Among these 34% also rely on bibliographic data.
- **Linguistic data** cover 30% of CQs. Among these, 77% also rely on bibliographic data, 19% on music data.
- 5% of all CQs require all 3 types of data.

We target bibliographic and historical data as a priority in the development of generic interfaces for music heritage exploration - assuming that a category shared by the majority of CQs is relevant to different target users.

Secondly, we performed a more detailed Exploratory Data Analysis to understand information patterns (entities and property patterns) to define strategies for content design and identify the main sections of the web portal ([EDA notebook](#) and [content design summary](#)).

In particular, each competency question can be described in terms of a starting node (i.e. an entity belonging to a class), an ending node, and a property path. For instance "Who is the composer of the music work?" has "Music Work" as starting node, a "Person" as ending node, and "has composer" as property path. A property path can be a

direct path or include intermediate nodes (e.g. "Where was a music work performed?" would require "Music Work" > "was performed in" > "Performance" > "took place in" > "Place"). In fig. 3.2 we summarise information patterns extracted from Competency Questions in a flow chart.

	CQ ID	Coverage	exp.	CQ	Bibl. data	Music data	Ling. data	User data	Main entities	Additional entities/props
Carolina	Carolina1-CQ1	full	-	Where was a musical composition performed?	yes	no	no	no	Musical performance: musical composition, place	
Carolina	Carolina1-CQ12	full	-	Which is the medium of performance of a musical composition?	yes	no	no	no	Musical performance: musical composition, medium	

Figure 3.1: Exemplar CQ annotated

Figure 3.2: Information patterns extracted from competency questions

The analysis of the most recurring patterns leads us to define 6 to 8 recurring discovery patterns which will be leveraged in the web portal as thematic sections. Sections can be summarised as follows:

- **Documentary evidence of topics.** Users have a topic in mind and look for documents referencing that topic. When exploring documents they want to know more about people (roles, audience), and connected topics.
- **Events connected to people.** Users have a person in mind and want to collect information on related events (e.g. performances, biographical events, historical context).
- **Soundscape of places.** Users have a place in mind and want to grab all music-related information that characterises the place, such as events, music works, and information on the history of instruments.
- **Networks around music genres.** Users have a genre (or composers relevant to the genre) in mind and want to discover people and works directly or indirectly related (e.g. influences).
- **Multimedia and music works.** Users have a piece of music in mind and want to retrieve scores, documents, and multimedia files. To find what they are looking for would require three entry points for searching (i.e. three sections in the final web portal), namely: by bibliographic metadata, by melodic patterns, or by lyrics.
- **Instruments** Users want to know more about the historical evolution of instruments.

Task analysis. Lastly, we classified CQs according to cognitive tasks ([task analysis](#)), so as to identify sets of CQs relevant to lay people and music experts, activities, and UX patterns. In Fig. 3.3 we graphically represent the distribution of tasks identified from Competency Questions.

Simple tasks (e.g. *share content*, *search content*, *learn more*) are categorised as being appropriate for lay people, and are therefore a target of the generic interfaces of the web portal. More sophisticated tasks (e.g. *answer a specific question*) are attributed to experts, and are therefore a target of data-driven stories, which are served via the web portal too.

From the task analysis we can estimate interaction patterns (i.e. the narrative that the web portal should respect) in order to incrementally serve informative needs of different target groups (from generic to experts). In particular, we looked at the co-occurrence of tasks and we classified patterns according to the background of related persona(s).

We then sorted them according to the (perceived) expertise of personas (from generic to experts). The proposed interaction patterns, based on the common pattern "overview first, and detail on demand" is typical of generous interfaces, and its validity is hereby confirmed by results of both the competitive analysis and focus groups. In detail:

Figure 3.3: Task analysis from Competency Questions

- Exploratory and discovery interfaces could be served first, proposing curiosities and interesting facts extracted from datasets to accommodate non-expert users (*Explore, Discover*)
- Curious and active users may decide to interact and personalise their feed, showing more/fewer data (*Share, Search, Personalise*)
- When expanding proposed stories, data visualizations contextualise data, along with relations with different data (*Learn more, Find relations between different content*)
- Experts that understand the value of data can continue their journey from here, being redirected to specialised dashboards for data exploration and interaction (*Find answer to specific questions*)

Competitive analysis We surveyed music-related websites ([benchmark table](#)) to define types of resources and characterise them according to UI/UX peculiarities, such as *information architecture, visual hierarchy of contents, interaction patterns, graphical choices*. We obtained a list of website types (i.e. streaming catalogues, music magazines and project/thematic websites) and their characteristics, to be used as a reference to design questionnaires in focus groups. In particular, we explored strategies for content organisation and information architecture, summarised

in Fig. 3.4. The majority of solutions use a *flat organisation of pages*, i.e. all pages of the website are at the same level and are accessible from the homepage. This solution works well when the web resource offers a small number of pages. The second most used strategy is the combination of *coexisting hierarchies of content*, that is, when competing information organisation strategies are provided, e.g. thematic sections referencing potentially overlapping content. All discovery patterns are served from a page that acts like a hub.

Figure 3.4: Competitive analysis - information architecture

Focus groups We interviewed around 150 bachelor's students with no music expertise (90% claim that they do not study or work in music-related fields) to collect user requirements for the web portal. The questionnaire is anonymous and no personal information is asked nor stored. We asked participants (1) to describe their habits, (2) to review two competitors, and (3) to provide feedback on several UI/UX aspects, highlighting expectations, frustration elements, and desiderata ([survey results](#) and [online form](#) with results statistics). Here are some highlights:

- The survey population represents **casual listeners**. The majority claims they do not listen to music regularly, and they mainly listen to music via a dedicated mobile app. Potentially, the listening experience happens as a background, secondary activity - the percentage of people claiming a constant interaction with the interface while playing music (e.g. add a like, a bookmark) is 60%.
- They are highly engaged with social media platforms, which are described as the most prominent **discovery channel** (92%), along with live events (e.g. interaction with friends and concerts). However, most students claim social media platforms are not the place where they store or share things they like or discover. Rather, 60% of participants claim they share content via instant messaging platforms, or save it for themselves only (they mention google keep, copy paste of texts or links, bookmarks in the browser).
- Possibly due to the lack of music education, **verbalised expectations** and desiderata from streaming application are shallow (e.g. recommendations based on the same artist, genre, or lyrics). The look and feel of the environment is considered important.
- When reading music information, topics must be grouped **thematically** (67%), with a simple scheme (only 46% claim that storytelling, demo or interactive guides are appreciated) and **progressive disclosure** of articles must be shown (68%). Usually, they do not open and read the whole article, but just skim the page, looking for something interesting (67%). External/internal links are highly appreciated. Moreover, they want to be able to see all about that theme (e.g. browsing an **archive**), not only suggested articles (68%).
- When they do interact with the application, they mostly do it to **create their tailored collection**, to create a

safe environment where only things they like appear (echo chamber effect). They like to be in control, and do not like automatic reproduction of contents they did not select.

Previous answers were confirmed by the interaction patterns with two specific websites, namely: [Spotify Fan Study](#) and [Expodcast](#). The majority of participants showed positive feelings. In Fun Study they appreciated the long scrolling of content, the progressive disclosure, and were attracted by the graphics and **data visualizations** (75%). In Expodcast 31% of users used the interactive guide, although they complained about the lack of clarity of contents and objectives of the website. The Fan Study interaction model was appreciated by 70% of participants when asked to pick the favourite website.

From results we get a number of suggestions to guide the design the UI/UX of the Web portal, and the confirmation that the interaction model proposed in the task analysis, similar to the one proposed in Fan Study, is potentially valid.

Web portal prototyping We designed the concept of the web portal taking into account aspects that emerged from competitive analysis, task analysis, and focus groups. We designed two main interaction patterns to explore the knowledge graph of Polifonia, namely: (1) a feed of recommended information cards in a magazine-like fashion, where contents are organised in thematic sections, and (2) an interactive visual search of the Polifonia *archive* to appreciate crosslinking in the knowledge graph ([prototype v.1](#)). We evaluated the initial prototype (mockups) with scholars that are members of the consortium. A full evaluation with generic users is postponed to later stages.

Dashboard development We developed *MELODY, Make mE a Linked Open DatastorY*, a flexible software that allows scholars to produce data stories via user-friendly interfaces. Data visualizations are produced by querying one or more SPARQL endpoints of the Polifonia knowledge graph and external sources. Scholars can select and preview charts derived from a SPARQL query, and these can be optionally accompanied by curated contents.

In detail, we designed requirements of MELODY so as to include peculiarities of both traditional dashboarding systems [24] and content management systems (CMS). Dashboard basic requirements include:

- **Visual displaying.** MELODY uses both graphics and text to effectively communicate the messages that the curators want to convey from a given dataset.
- **Fit single screen.** Single visualizations must fit the device dimensions, so that they can be fully appreciated. In MELODY we respect as much as possible this rule, taking into account that more sophisticated arrangements of content would require charts and long captions to be displayed together.
- **Customisation.** MELODY can be used with any online dataset provided with a SPARQL endpoint. Several graphic templates and different types of graphs can be selected.

CMS basic requirements include:

- **Creation.** content creation is simplified through the use of a What You See Is What You Get (WYSIWYG) interface to query and preview charts.
- **Management.** a JSON configuration file stores SPARQL queries and methods for arranging and displaying them as content, without storing data.
- **Publishing.** Data stories are published as web-ready documents, according to several templates, which automatically place content according to pagination rules. Charts and stories can be exported in other formats.
- **Presentation.** Templates allow to customize some pagination aspects (e.g. color palette, width and positioning of charts / texts)

The software is developed in Python and Flask. The source code of the dashboarding system is available on Github⁸. Data stories produced by pilots will be integrated in the web portal, linked to articles addressing related content. A full evaluation of the software is postponed to later stages of the project.

Templates prototyping To design templates for the dashboarding system, i.e. select which data visualizations are in scope and which interaction patterns are needed, we refined the methodology used in the Competency Questions analysis. We reviewed the distant-reading approach used to cluster information patterns, and we pursued a more systematic, question-driven approach, based on close-reading of CQs.

⁸<https://github.com/polifonia-project/dashboard>

We selected pilots that are not producing their own interface, namely, *MEETUPS*, *MUSICBO*, *BELLS*, *CHILD*, *ORGANS*, *TUNES*. Currently we excluded *INTERLINK*, *FACETS*, and *TONALITIES* since these are producing their own interfaces. For each pilot, we analysed personas and we identified four macro-categories based on personas' background and research interests, namely:

- **Music historians** interested in temporal and spatial analysis (of events and networks). This group is relevant to *MEETUPS*, *MUSICBO*, *CHILD* and *BELLS*.
- **Musicologists** interested in distributional aspects, networks, and clusters of music features over time. This group is relevant to *TUNES* and *ORGANS*.
- **Creative industries** interested in interlinking, statistical relations and overviews. This group overlaps with historians of *CHILD*, and stakeholders of *INTERLINK*.
- **Music producers** interested in network relations and serendipitous discovery.

The last category (music producers) is not exclusively targeted by any pilot, although several stories addressing such personas also cover interests that significantly overlap with goals of the Web portal. For this reason we discard the category in the design of dashboards and we address it in the design of generic (generous) interfaces.

From categories and research interests we can deduce a classification of **data types and visualization templates**, namely: geo-located data (maps), time-series (line charts, bar charts, scatter plots), and statistical data (the previous data visualizations plus donuts, flows, etc.).

To design interaction patterns in identified data visualizations we reviewed stories connected to each group and we designed a **data story** for each pilot, specifically with the aim to address the added value of the pilot dataset and provide an overview of its data. We looked for **driver questions**, i.e. those CQs that drive all the sub-questions. Driver questions are the ones initiating a visualization, defining which data points populate the chart or map. Other questions are aggregated to define other elements of the visualization, e.g. popups, search areas, and filtering systems, and their content.

In Fig. 3.5 we show as an example the workflow for designing an interface for *MEETUPS*. David is a music historian interested in the analysis of performances. He needs to place performances in a map and to derive conclusions on performed music and audience.

Figure 3.5: MEETUPS data story design

Evaluation We had a focus group with scholars in the Polifonia consortium to validate the usability of interfaces (via their mockups) and we collected suggestions and improvements to be applied to forthcoming versions of the prototype and the dashboard. To test the dashboard system and data visualization templates, we designed one data story for each pilot, and we asked scholars to evaluate the mockup. We used 20 heuristics [25] to summarise potential problems from the point of view of experts.

4 Software outputs, results and evaluation

The Web portal is meant to be a composite artefact that satisfies requirements of different user groups via dedicated routes. Results of this task consist of several components. An overview of the final ecosystem is graphically represented in Fig. 4.1:

Figure 4.1: Overview of the Web portal components and simplified architecture

In this deliverable we present the following components, namely:

- (dataset and online catalogue) musoW , the **catalogue** of online music resources that helps us to improve music data findability
- (software) CLEF, the **web application** for manually populating musoW
- (software) the pipeline for discovering, classifying, and **recommending** online music resources and semi-automatically populating musoW catalogue
- (graphic prototype) graphic mockup of the Polifonia **website** presenting music heritage data to a broad audience and to allow advanced search on Polifonia Knowledge graph, to showcase the potential of integrated, interlinked, data
- (software) a **dashboarding system** to produce web-ready, data-driven stories. Stories will be linked from the web portal to lead curious and expert users in a data-driven presentation of Polifonia data.
- (graphic prototype) three graphic templates leveraged by the dashboard system to present data according to different views, and **six data stories** based on the three aforementioned templates, exemplifying the potential of Polifonia pilots.

4.1 Cataloguing: the *musoW* registry of music heritage on the Web

Summary. *musoW* 2.0 is the online registry of music resources on the web. A web application is available online for data exploration at <http://w3id.org/musow/>. A copy of the dataset is stored on GitHub¹ and Zenodo². Currently, the registry includes descriptions of around 500 online music resources, including detailed metadata about their scope, their audience, the type of data served, and the data access points³. We chose to use the name *musoW* in continuity with a prior project, mentioned in section 2, developed by some members of Polifonia. *musoW* Linked Open Dataset is an ancillary resource that will support the Polifonia web portal in harvesting and discovering relevant music data on the web. Despite its intended auxiliary role, *musoW* is a self-standing resource that can be of benefit to several stakeholders, such as music journalists, librarians, teachers, and scholars in musicology.

The **online website** is the main access point to the registry. From the homepage (Fig. 4.2a) users can read about the project, log in to modify existing records, add new records in anonymous mode, or get technical details (about the data model, the SPARQL endpoint, and the backup copy of the dataset on GitHub).

Figure 4.2: *musoW* homepage and functionalities

The website allows users to **search the *musoW* registry** in two ways, namely: a full-text search to retrieve resources by name or keywords, and a filter-based exploratory interface to provide an overview of surveyed resources grouped by relevant metadata, such as title, creator, type, audience, task, and other categories (Fig. 4.2b). Filters correspond to fields used to describe resources, and can be easily added/removed from the back-end of the web application.

Users can **anonymously contribute** to the catalogue by filling in a user-friendly form (Fig. 4.3a). The cataloguing system supports users in resources disambiguation, e.g. when they suggest a resource that may already be in *musoW*, and with auto-completion suggestions from Wikidata and *musoW* itself (Fig. 4.3b). Users' contributions are reviewed by members of an editorial board before being published. The editorial board potentially includes any person with a GitHub account that is registered a collaborator on the [GitHub organization](#) or the [repository of *musoW*](#). People willing to become an editor (and change existing records) must therefore request access to the Polifonia organisation.

Since the first publication of *musoW* registry in November 2021, we have increased the **number of surveyed resources** to 500 (+42%), thanks to external contributions (which provided both new records and requests to modify existing ones) and a 2-hour hackathon with 10 Polifonia members to boost the inclusion of new entries. New records mostly address online music archives and datasets for music analysis tasks.

On average, 10-20 users per day visit the website, and spend around 4-5 minutes per session (Fig. 4.4). The peak in April corresponds to the new release of CLEF, advertised on social media. Results are in line with the KPIs specified in the Grant Agreement (Table 1.1 Objective and results).

¹ *musoW* data on GitHub, https://github.com/polifonia-project/registry_app/tree/main/records

² *musoW* data on Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/badge/latest/doi/368253077>

³ See an example record: DoReMus, <https://projects.dharc.unibo.it/musow/view-1635268063-595922>

Figure 4.3: musoW crowdsourcing functionalities

Figure 4.4: musoW visits between November 2021 and April 2022

The **dataset** is freely available for reuse under a [CC0 waiver](#). It can be programmatically accessed via a dedicated [SPARQL endpoint](#), a [data dump on GitHub](#), and on [Zenodo](#).

4.2 Crowdsourcing: CLEF

Summary. *Crowdsourcing Linked Entities via web Form (CLEF)* [26] is an agile LOD-native platform for collaborative data collection, peer-review, and publication. In particular, the strong focus on user-friendly interfaces for producing findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data, a provenance-aware editorial process, and the integration with consolidated data management workflows, distinguish CLEF as a novel attempt to develop Linked Data platforms for cultural heritage. In Polifonia, we use and continuously develop CLEF to populate the *musoW* registry. The source code is available on [GitHub](#)⁴. Being largely customisable via user-friendly interfaces, CLEF can accommodate requirements of many small-medium crowdsourcing projects beyond Polifonia.

Overview. CLEF is a highly configurable application that allows anyone to build their own crowdsourcing platform, to integrate the data management workflow with Linked Open Data standards and popular development and community platforms, and immediately enjoy high-quality data with exploratory tools. CLEF is a web-based application in which users can describe resources (e.g. real-world entities, concepts, digital resources) via intuitive web forms. To help with entering descriptions, users are offered auto-complete suggestions from vocabularies, existing records and terms automatically extracted from text. The templating system of CLEF is configurable via a web interface, in which each form field for describing the resource is mapped to an ontology predicate chosen by the administrators.

⁴<https://github.com/polifonia-project/clef>

Templates are the main drivers of the application, since they ensure consistency in data entry and data validation, they guide the peer-review of records, and are fundamental in retrieval and exploration via actionable filters. Both authenticated and anonymous contributions can be enabled. A simple peer-review mechanism allows users to curate their records, publish them, and continuously populate the catalogue of contents, which can be immediately browsed via automatically generated interfaces and filters. CLEF is designed to be easily integrated with GitHub and simplify the data management workflow, naturally supporting several of the FAIR requirements.

Fig. 4.5 presents an overview of the CLEF data management system. In detail, CLEF allows an administrator to configure and customise the application via user-friendly interfaces. In the **configuration** setup, users can specify information relevant to their dataset, e.g. URI base, prefix, SPARQL endpoint API (with default configuration), and optional mechanisms for version control and user authentication (via GitHub). The setup of dereferencing mechanisms is delegated to the adopter, who can choose and set up redirection rules by means of their favourite persistent URI provider (e.g. [w3id](#)).

Figure 4.5: CLEF overview

For each type of resources to be collected and described, a **template** is created in the form of a JSON mapping document. This includes form field types (e.g. text box, checkbox, dropdown), expected values (literals, entities), services to be called (e.g. autocomplete based on Wikidata and the catalogue, Named Entity Recognition in long texts), the mapping between fields and ontology terms or controlled vocabularies, and whether the field should be used in a default web page, called *Explore*, as a filter to aggregate data.

Ontology terms and terms from controlled vocabularies specified by users are managed via the **vocabulary** module. It's worth noting that, while users can specify their own ontology terms, CLEF fosters reuse of popular and standard vocabularies. The module updates the CLEF triplestore with user-specified terms (which may be new terms or terms belonging to existing ontologies) and calls the APIs of *LOV Linked Open Vocabularies* [22] to retrieve original labels and comments associated with reused terms. The resulting data model is shown in a dedicated web page called *Data Model* along with information retrieved from LOV.

The **form** for data entry is generated according to settings specified in templates. While editing (creating, modifying, or reviewing) a record, both CLEF triplestore and external **services** like [SpaCy](#) and Wikidata APIs are called to provide suggestions. Every time a record is created/modified, data are sent to the **ingestion** module. The latter performs a first validation of the form based on the associated templates, and calls the **mapping** module, which transforms data into RDF according to ontology terms specified in the template and updates the named graph created for the record.

CLEF supports a compliant SPARQL 1.1 [27] endpoint as back-end. Current running instances use Blazegraph [28]. In particular, named graphs are extensively used to annotate and retrieve provenance information needed to manage the peer-review process, and to efficiently serve record-related information in the exploratory interfaces.

A module is dedicated to the interaction with **GitHub**. GitHub was chosen for its popularity as a dissemination platform for versioned code and data, which fosters visibility of project results, and for its services - i.e., APIs for read-write operations, OAuth mechanisms. Users may decide to bind their application to a GitHub repository, which allows them (1) to store a backup of data in a public/private repository, (2) to keep track of every change to data via commits, and (3) to enable user authentication to the web application via [GitHub OAuth](#). At the moment, we are working on an alternative login system for a more traditional access control system.

Lastly, to increase findability of collections, a few **automatically generated web pages** serve browsing and search interfaces over the catalogue. Currently CLEF provides the following templates: a homepage; the backend controller from which to access the list of records, the setup configuration form and the templates forms; records creation/modification/review and publication forms; a *Documentation* page with instructions on the usage of forms; the

Explore page, where views on collected data are shown and filtered; a template to display the records wherein Linked Open Data are also served as RDFa annotations; a template to display controlled vocabulary terms and statistics on their usage in the catalogue; a *Data model* page, collecting ontology terms and definitions from LOV; and a GUI to query the SPARQL endpoint.

Evaluation. Existing software and initiatives do not address all our three main requirements - i.e. user-friendliness for final users (UF-U) and administrators (UF-A), provenance management (PM), and data management integration (DMI). Moreover, researchers have argued that solutions developed for a single institution or project turn out not to be sustainable or not motivating for users [29]. Therefore we also consider sustainability and reusability out of the original context (SR) when reviewing prior works. An overview of systems surveyed in section 2 and their characteristics is shown in table 4.1.

Name	UF-U	UF-A	PM	DMI	SR
LED	✓	✓	✓	✓	
OmekaS	✓	✓			✓
Semantic MediaWiki	✓	✓	✓		✓
Sinopia	✓	✓			✓
ResearchSpace	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 4.1: Overview of systems for collaborative data collection and Linked Data publishing

LED complies with most of our functional requirements, however it is not reusable as-is. Omeka S and Sinopia do not allow a full-fledged peer-review process. Semantic Media Wiki is not integrated with any existing data management workflows (same as Omeka S and Sinopia). ResearchSpace is highly configurable and reusable, although it requires admins with technical skills to be continuously available for the setup and changes of final interfaces. In conclusion, CLEF results being a lightweight, pragmatic, reusable interface for LOD production and publication that outperforms existing solutions.

4.3 Discovery: Pipeline for discovery and musoW population

Summary. The pipeline for populating musoW includes (1) a Twitter search engine for posts addressing music resources, (2) a classifier of tweets, (3) a web scraper of music web resources referenced in tweets, (4) a text summariser of descriptions included in scraped websites, (5) and classifier of descriptions, and (6) a recommending system of resources to be manually reviewed and included in musoW.

Currently, the pipeline is stored as a [Jupyter notebook](#) for reproducibility purposes. The script is run on a regular basis to collect new music resources. It is based on Logistic Regression and TF-IDF as the main feature to classify texts. In table 4.2 we present results of classifiers to identify Tweets and music resources.⁵

Preliminary evaluation. We created a dataset of Twitter posts to test (a) the goodness of keywords used for the initial Twitter search, (b) precision of returned true positive web resources, eventually pruning those based on irrelevant keywords. The dataset and the evaluation are available online⁶.

Figure 4.6: Keywords and positive predictions

⁵We used cross-validation (10 folds) to avoid overfitting. Currently, we do not perform any particular hyperparameters tuning other than tokenizing bigrams and limiting the number of tokens to 1000.

⁶<https://github.com/polifonia-project/musow-pipeline/tree/master/EVAL>

Classifier	Precision (0)	Precision (1)	Recall (0)	Recall (1)	F1
Twitter	0.93	0.97	0.98	0.92	0.95
Web resources	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.96

Table 4.2: Twitter and Music resource classifier: precision, recall, f1

The Twitter search was run for tweets from January to April 2022 and set to return 50 tweets for each keyword bigram extracted from musoW (21 in total) a month. It returned 4200 tweets. We classified tweets and we collected the URLs of music resources mentioned in positive tweets, which were in turn scraped, summarised, and classified. The classifier returned 525 (positively predicted) results. We saved positive results in a spreadsheet for manual inspection.

Figure 4.7: Pruned keywords and positive predictions

In Fig. 4.6 we show the distribution of manually annotated positive/negative results for each keyword. Out of 525 results, 21% (107) are actual good candidates for inclusion in musoW, while the remaining 79% (418) of predicted results are not suitable for inclusion in musoW ($p=0.2$), since retrieved resources do not provide any data.

We reused the results of the evaluation to target issues, estimate future steps, and to eventually improve results

of the recommender. In detail, we investigated which keywords were at the origin of the most false positive results. We decide to prune all results based on keywords that return fewer than 5 true positive results, and we obtain a subset of 207 results, out of which 40% (83) are now true positive results ($p=0.4, r=0.8$) and 124 are false positive results. In summary, we now consider the following keywords for Twitter search: *audio file*, *music archive*, *music collection*, *music library*, *sheet music*, *sound archive*, *sound recording* (Fig. 4.7).

4.4 Design and exploration: the Web portal and dashboards

In section 4.4.1 below we present prototypes of the web portal and data stories together, to showcase the expected user journey from generic interfaces to specialised ones. In section 4.4.2 we present the dashboarding system.

4.4.1 The web portal and data stories

Summary. The prototype of the Web portal is designed to accommodate lay users in discovering music heritage data. It includes two main interaction patterns, namely: a homepage showing a stream of thematic sections (called *feed*) and an interactive search on the archive of the Polifonia knowledge graph (called *tuner mode*). The prototype is available online.⁷

Overview. The homepage presents the scope of the web portal (Fig. 4.10) and a carousel of **highlights**. Highlights are entities or concepts belonging to 8 categories (topics, tunes, genres, lyrics, scores, people, places, instruments) that characterise a theme (Fig. 4.8b). A theme is a collection of concepts semantically interlinked in a meaningful way (e.g. a topic recurring in documents and lyrics associated to tunes of a certain genre produced in a city).

Scrolling the homepage, highlighted topics appear again as subjects of **thematic sections** (Fig. 4.8c). Each section is composed of a title including the highlight, a list of results (i.e. entities from the Polifonia KG related to the highlight), and some filters to prune results and provide insights of interest. Results can be of different types, according to the nature of the highlight, and they are meant to address relevant, recurring, competency questions that emerged in the preliminary analysis (described in section 3.2.4). The user can change the subject of the section (the highlight) and see the list of results and filters changing accordingly.

⁷https://github.com/polifonia-project/web_portal/tree/main/prototypes

Figure 4.8: The Web portal - feed prototype

When clicking on a result, a card showing **insights** appears (Fig. 4.8d). The card includes textual information available for that entity, links to related cards (e.g. topics, documents, performances), links to external sources (if available), call for actions like *share*, *listen on Spotify*, or *Read lyrics on Genius* if applicable, and a chart contextualising the entity and its main attributes (e.g. all performances of an artist's works over time). Insights and exploratory visualisations are designed according to the content design strategy described in section 3.2.4. More external links (e.g. to resources described in musoW) will be designed to foster interlinking and integration.

Notice that if the entity described in the card is referenced in a pilot-related data story, a direct link to dashboards is provided (for experts). For instance, performances are a subject of interest in MEETUPS. The user is redirected to a web page presenting the pilot story (Fig. 4.9a) and including insights of the dataset explored. In the case of MEETUPS, an interactive map is shown (Fig. 4.9b) along with preset filters (defined by the author of the story). The user can explore and select data points (Fig. 4.9c) - in this case, performances. A right sidebar shows insights about the selected point (Fig. 4.9d), which may include interactive charts to better frame the context of the data point, e.g. instrument analysis.

From the top-right menu users can access the **tuner**, which works like an interactive search of the archive of the Polifonia KG. A brief explanation of main features introduces the user to the search (Fig. 4.10a). Users can select types of information they would like to combine by clicking on the top horizontal menu (i.e. labels previously representing thematic sections).

For each label, a list of most representative highlights is presented (Fig. 4.10b), e.g. most recurring topics in documents mentioned in Polifonia KG. The user can select one or more highlight for each label, which will appear on the right sidebar as a reminder. Alternatively the user can search via a full text search, and can filter the scope of results using filters via filters on the right (e.g. by time span).

(a) Data story introduction

(b) Data visualization and filters

(c) Data point insights

(d) Exploratory visualizations related to data points

Figure 4.9: Data stories - MEETUPS prototype

Once the selection of terms of interest is completed, the user runs the search and retrieves a sorted list of results (Fig. 4.10c). Results are accompanied by their category (e.g. a document, a performance) and the explanation of the relation with selected search criteria (e.g. documents mentioning "harmony" as a topic, or tunes of genre "classical music", or related to a person like "Mozart"). Different types of results can appear (e.g. documents, performances, people), and can be sorted / pruned according to the type of result (2nd column) or the relations (3rd column). When clicking on a result, a card like in fig. 4.8d is shown.

UI/UX design considerations. The concept is inspired by the mechanisms of a **music box** (carillon). We reused the brand identity of Polifonia to provide a consistent look and feel to the Web portal. We used **colors** of the logo to distinguish thematic sections and give a clear identity to the different pieces of information that characterise Polifonia KG. To enforce the concept, background colors change while scrolling the initial carousel (Fig. 4.8b), when scrolling over a section (Fig. 4.8c), and when reading the insights of a specific topic (Fig. 4.8d).

When scrolling the carousel, small **music** effects are played as soon as a card appears in the lower part of the screen. Sound can be muted and in any case affects only the introductory part of the exploration. Every color/theme corresponds to a sound. The combination of colors and themes generates a melody, hence *playing the soundtrack* of a story related to music heritage. Ideally, the web portal works like a magazine, and the carousel of highlights and related sections change on a regular basis, so as to **encourage users to return** to the website and see different insights. Optimal strategies for content interlinking and recommendation will be the subject of the next phases of development.

The **information architecture** respects criteria highlighted in the competitive analysis, i.e. co-existing hierarchies of content providing different access points to (potentially) the same information, as well as a simple thematic organisation of contents. Both strategies were positively judged by lay users in focus groups. **Progressive disclosure**

Figure 4.10: The Web portal - archive prototype

of articles in the feed, the overview of highlights in the initial carousel, and the exploratory interface to search the archive respect best practices of *generous interfaces*, hence encouraging curious or lazy users to explore something unknown and preventing them from getting frustrated.

Lastly, the menu (Fig. 4.10d, top-left) includes shortcuts to the most important information, sorted by complexity of expected target users, namely: the feed, the archive, the data stories, and a description of the project. It also includes the footer of the website, where more specialised information can be found (e.g. access to data).

Evaluation. To foster co-creation and evaluate the initial version of the web portal and data stories, we continuously asked for feedback in the consortium, via the survey presented in D1.2, and via two **focus groups** with domain experts of the Polifonia consortium. According to J. Nielsen⁸, sessions with five users are sufficient to identify 85% of usability problems. While we privileged the discussion with music scholars, we asked scholars with other expertise to join in the sessions and contribute to the discussion.

We interviewed two music historians, two musicologists, one music technology expert, one web designer, one data curator, and one AI expert. The full report is available online⁹. We first presented the mockups, then we introduced participants to the structure of the questionnaires (one for the web portal and one for the data stories), wherein we asked them to summarise their opinions at the end of the session.

The questionnaire is structured on the 20 heuristics identified by Weinschenk and Barker [25], and it focuses on **potential errors and violations** rather than on expectations and appreciated features. Collected feedback will be used to revise prototypes in version 2. Contributions from participants can be summarised as follows:

⁸<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/why-you-only-need-to-test-with-5-users/>

⁹https://github.com/polifonia-project/web_portal/blob/main/questionnaires/Polifonia%20Web%20portal_%20Expert%20Usability%20Review.pdf

Web portal

- *Music historians* are interested in specialised search interfaces. Searching for an entity via thematic sections (Fig. 4.8c) is deemed insufficient to discover documentary evidence on their research topics. Rather, an immediate route to reach the advanced search is appreciated.
- *AI developers, Music technologists and Musicologists* are interested in the heuristics used for **content recommendation**. Metrics used to design the initial carousel (i.e. how highlights are connected) and results in the archive search should be clearly explained to users.
- *All participants* appreciated the website concept, although the labels *Feed* and *tuner mode* were not immediately understood (also depending on the age of participants). They all prefer a **simpler labelling**. Likewise, all experts stressed the need for explanations accompanying the feed.

Data stories

- *Music historians* appreciated the statistics template and the possibility to combine charts and explanations. However, they usually perform qualitative research by close-reading documents summarised in charts. Hence, they would like to have **access to the full-text of documents or tunes** referenced in charts.
- *Musicologists* appreciated the interactive chart for data integration and temporal analysis. They stressed the need to **provide more filters** to choose from. However, *Music technologists* would prefer these to be defined a priori by the dashboard designer, since asking the user to visually create filters/facets may be overwhelming. Moreover, effective means to visualize and query melodic patterns should be defined in the next stage of development.

4.4.2 MELODY. The dashboarding system

Summary. *MELODY, Make mE a Linked Open Data storY*, is a dashboarding system that allows expert users to create web-ready data stories based on one or more Linked Open Datasets. Data stories can be linked or exported in several formats. Three graphic templates can be selected to create different types of data stories, namely: a geographical map, an interactive timeline, and mixed-chart statistics. Currently, only the graphic template for statistics is implemented. The source code of the dashboard is available online.¹⁰

In detail, MELODY is a web-based, reusable, and user-friendly solution for retrieving, presenting, and publishing Linked Data in the form of Data Stories. The core components of the project are:

- A Python application developed with the Flask framework.
- A JSON configuration file that includes the application and all data stories setup information
- A set of HTML templates for the application and the data stories.
- A set of Ajax HTTP requests to query SPARQL endpoints, manipulate results, and create charts.

In Fig. 4.11 we showcase the journey of a Data story designer in MELODY. The welcome page (fig. 4.11a) presents available data stories on the left grouped under section names (which in the context of Polifonia will be the pilot names), and redirects the user to the **authentication** via GitHub. Currently, only members of the Polifonia organisation can access the backend of the application, but in the future it will be extended to any user with a GitHub account. After the login, the user is redirected to the **setup page of a new story** (Fig. 4.11b). In the setup page, the user is asked to select the template from a gallery. The user can click on a template icon to see details of the look and feel of the template. So far, only the statistics template is implemented. Secondly, the user can pick an existing section (visible from the sidebar) or can create a new one. Lastly, the main title of the story and the SPARQL endpoint of the data source are entered.

After submission, the user is redirected to a **WYSIWYG form** (What You See Is What You Get) that imitates the final data story pagination (Fig. 4.11c). Here the user can choose the color palette, enter text content, such as title, author, description, and can create visualizations. With respect to proposed visualizations, currently the user

¹⁰<https://github.com/polifonia-project/dashboard>

Figure 4.11: MELODY dashboards

can choose to create a counter, a bar chart, line chart, or doughnut chart (Fig. 4.11d). The user enters a SPARQL query and specifies a few details (e.g. the title of the chart, the labels, the positioning in the page) and a preview is immediately shown with the results of the query. The user can save changes and modify the data story.

Once the story has been saved, the **web-ready data story** can be accessed from the left sidebar. It presents the content arranged according to the user's preferences (Fig. 4.11e), along with details of the authors and the data source used to create the story. Both the story and the **individual charts can be exported** for reuse (Fig. 4.11f). The story can be exported as a web-ready static web document and as a PDF. Likewise, individual charts can be exported as images, or directly embedded in external webpages.

5 Discussion and conclusion

Cataloguing. To the best of our knowledge, the musoW registry is currently the biggest dataset on online music-related resources available on the Web. Moreover, it is the only catalogue of its kind that provides data as Linked Open Data, offering several data access points to programmatically query the data and therefore making the data easy to reuse in external applications. It is also worth noting that it is the only catalogue of its kind that includes more than 50 descriptive fields, and that can be explored via user-friendly interfaces for browsing and search. To this extent, musoW differentiates itself from prior attempts as a fully-fledged web application for music data discovery.

Crowdsourcing. CLEF is a pragmatic solution to solve the collaborative creation of Linked Open Datasets via a user-friendly web environment. Compared to existing solutions, it provides admin-friendly interfaces to customise record templates and filtering interfaces. Moreover, it is the only software that allows users to integrate existing data management workflows, e.g. GitHub, Zenodo, Internet Archive, Wikidata direct reuse.

Discovery. While several pipelines exist to accomplish similar desiderata in different fields (e.g. to create [Machine Learning newsletters](#)), the pipeline for music resources discovery is unique in its genre. It relies on consolidated technologies that are easy to deploy in production environments. Results show that more work has to be done to improve the precision of recommendations (minimum target: 0.8). Alternative approaches for text classification could be considered, e.g. BERT [30], which however requires GPU and (many) CPU to fine-tune a model. In recent years, a few approaches to distill language models have been proposed [31, 32] and could be the subject of further development to improve our classifier.

5.1 Reusability of results

musoW is currently used by scholars in Polifonia and outside the consortium to explore the landscape of music heritage on the web. Stakeholders include also professionals, like music journalists and music librarians (already engaged in the design of the registry). **CLEF** is of interest to a broad community, especially to those scholars or institutions that cannot afford commercial products or that do not have technical skills in house to deploy complex systems. Such a scenario is common in the Cultural Heritage domain. Likewise, the **dashboarding system** fills in a gap in the state of art for LOD exploratory analysis and storytelling, and it is highly reusable with any kind of Linked Data. Currently, only users of the Polifonia project can access it. In the near future we will open up the possibility to use the software to all users with a github account, granting the possibility to publish for free their stories on a dedicated repository as static web pages. Potentially, CLEF and MELODY can be combined to provide a comprehensive solution to handle the life-cycle of LOD - from creation, to publication, exploration and preservation. The **pipeline for populating musoW** can be used as-is, regardless of the actual interaction with musoW, to create newsletters. While its reuse on different scopes is not planned, developers can reuse our approach to develop similar pipelines and create their own recommender.

5.2 Limitations and future works

Cataloguing and discovery. Despite being so far the most comprehensive online catalogue of music resources, musoW suffers from issues typical of crowdsourced collections, namely: completeness and accuracy of metadata. To improve the completeness of the catalogue we developed the pipeline for data discovery. In future works we will extend the search and classifier to Reddit, GitHub and others. The current status of the recommender does not provide a complete set of metadata for the resource described (only URL, title, and description), and the cataloguing is delegated to the human reviewer. In future works we will pair the pipeline for knowledge discovery with a dedicated **pipeline for data enrichment**, targeting the most important pieces of information for the cataloguing. Moreover, we

will deploy an online service, with an UI and public API, to simplify its reuse and to easily integrate results into musoW - so that recommendations appear as suggested records into the online system.

Web portal and data stories templates. WP1.T3 activities officially started in June 2021. Most activities focused on the design and development of the musoW registry, while the development and deployment of the web portal was postponed to after the first release of the pilots datasets (which overlaps with this deliverable). Therefore we can envision and draft the final result, but we are not currently able to provide a full-fledged working demo. This limitation turned into an opportunity, as it allowed us to address common problems and develop reusable interfaces (i.e. CLEF, MELODY) and to foster co-creation in the design. However, we may **iteratively revisit the prototype** in the next months to comply with unexpected, pilot-dependent, requirements. Likewise, we evaluated mockups of the web portal with domain experts, who are not the (only) primary target. In the near future we will perform usability tests with general users, to monitor the development and the potential impact of the web portal.

Dashboard. Likewise, the design of a flexible, template-based, dashboard system allows us to predict a number of scenarios that are common across pilots, but more scenarios may come up in the future. Moreover, despite the tool being designed to require as few technical skills as possible, extensive knowledge of Linked Open Data is still required to set up a data story (e.g. to write a SPARQL query). While in the first phase we will support domain experts in the design and implementation of stories, future developments will tackle **user friendly solutions for writing SPARQL queries** so as to facilitate reuse of the dashboard also for non LOD-experts, and will provide bespoke solutions for manipulating structured music data.

A draft of the work plan for the next months is the following:

- Pipeline for data discovery and enrichment
 - Revision, improvement, and deployment of the discovery pipeline by December 2022
 - Pipeline for data enrichment and integration with musoW by March 2023
- Dashboard and data stories
 - Revision, and new templates implemented by March 2023
 - Creation of at least one story pilot by June 2023
- Web portal
 - Web portal online with pilots data and musoW registry integrated by December 2022
 - Integration of data stories in the Web portal by June 2023
 - Heuristics for stories and music data recommendation by October 2023
 - Integration of external data sources in the Web portal by December 2023
 - User evaluation by March 2024

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